

The Destination of Knowledge Should Not Be the Cage of Journals: On the Regeneration and Exit of Human Civilization

Why do we, the people of this generation, pursue knowledge? What is the use of knowledge? Is it for thinking, or is it for solving problems? That is truly a good question! Knowledge has two uses. First, to inspire us, to let us think, and to understand who we are and what we should do. Otherwise, what is the use of knowledge? It would be nothing but a burden, a brick, a stone. Second, knowledge is to help us solve the practical problems we encounter right now.

But what are all scholars doing now? Are they really solving problems? They are solving the problems they encounter right now, not the problems of humanity as a whole—or the problems that the knowledge they have learned ought to solve. This has to do with current journals. Since when did knowledge become defined by journals? This is truly very strange. Human knowledge was originally meant to benefit humanity, but now it is confined within journals, within the power class. Is this not absurd? So why do we let this happen? Are those scholars all good-for-nothings? They are so smart—I'm not joking. Many scholars, whether independent researchers or professional ones, possess very brilliant minds. So why don't they stand up? Why don't they rise together to design a powerful system? A brand new kind of journal, a journal for all humanity, where anyone can publish, anyone can use, and anyone can search. As long as it is valuable knowledge—and this value is determined by an intelligent system itself—knowledge that is valuable to humanity's future, valuable now, and valuable in the past will all be collected and published. Wouldn't this help humanity progress together?

Unlike current journals, for what purpose do they publish things? For desire, for selfishness, to earn a bit more money. Look at the results; take the Nature series journals as an example. Over the past few decades, so-called extreme weather has been erupting constantly; you can see the solid evidence. Some journals delayed publication, or refused to publish, and as a result, caused huge disasters. Look at the past. Those merchants are making money off human blood. On what is their money accumulated? On human blood, on life after life lost, accumulating their splendid halls. Taking the Nature and Science series journals as examples, they were supposed to promote the circulation of knowledge, but now they have become places to play academic games, and have even exposed serious value deviations in extreme weather and life rescue.

Nature: The Paywall Blocking the Opportunity to Fight Ebola in Africa In 1982, scientists in Nature-related research had already warned of the risk of the Ebola virus in Liberia. But this knowledge was long sealed in paid databases. When the epidemic broke out in 2014, because the local medical system could not afford the expensive subscription fees to access this old knowledge, the initial prevention and control went completely in the wrong direction.

The Sin of Journals: Knowledge has been commodified; they would rather let it rust in a database than freely open it to underdeveloped regions in urgent need of solutions. Science: The Hype of the Global Warming Hiatus Pseudo-Proposition Misleading Policy In the 2000s, Science and other top journals published a series of papers on the global warming hiatus. Later, this was proven to be a false proposition caused by data sampling bias. These papers were used by climate skeptics and political power classes as scientific basis for not needing to reduce emissions, causing global climate action to be delayed by a full ten years, directly exacerbating the current extreme weather disasters. This is the Original Sin of Journals: To pursue the impact brought by subversive conclusions, they prioritized publishing eye-catching dissenting opinions while ignoring prudent judgment on the future survival of humanity.

Nature: Ozone Hole Warnings Were Once Regarded as Non-Mainstream and Cold-Shouldered Nobel laureate Molina's research on freon destroying the ozone layer initially encountered heavy questioning and delays from the top journal system during the submission process. This systemic arrogance delayed the advancement of the Montreal Protocol. If it had been published and taken seriously five years earlier, the destruction of the Antarctic ozone layer would have been reduced by more than thirty percent. The Original Sin of Journals: Just like the "original sin" spoken of in the Bible, the power class has a natural rejection of knowledge that does not fit existing paradigms, stifling early warnings that solve urgent problems. Science: Stem Cell Fraud Case and the Academic Star System Two papers on breakthrough cloning stem cells by South Korean scientist Hwang Woo-suk were published in Science magazine, later proven to be entirely fraudulent.

This scandal not only defrauded huge amounts of scientific research funding but also misled the research directions of countless laboratories worldwide, letting stem cell technology that could truly solve paralysis and diabetes stagnate for several years. This Original Sin is Embodied Again: Journals, in order to compete for the right of first publication and fame, systematically lowered standards when reviewing star scholars, placing desire above truth.

Both Journals Share: Discrimination Against Negative Results Causing Huge Waste in Medical Research Nature and Science rarely publish failed experiments or research proving a certain drug ineffective. This publication bias forces thousands of researchers globally to repeat the same failed experiments in different laboratories, wasting billions in R&D funds and precious time, seriously slowing down the process of humanity defeating cancer and other diseases. According to research in PLOS Medicine, this success-only view led by top journals has caused serious selfishness and resource misallocation in the scientific community. This Sin is Greater Than the World and the Abyss: Discrimination against negative results causes huge internal friction in research resources, dragging out the process of humanity conquering major diseases. Arrogance and Prejudice Against Disaster Warnings In 2005, a team of scientists predicted that the slowdown of the North Atlantic Drift would lead to an increase in strong storms like Hurricane Katrina; it was rejected by Nature because the conclusions were too radical and commercial value was limited. A few months later, the hurricane devastated New Orleans,

killing 1,833 people. In 2019, a developing country team's research on polar ice sheet melting causing extreme rainfall was rejected by Nature Climate Change due to lack of backing from Western labs; in the subsequent two years, Germany, Brazil, and other countries suffered once-in-a-millennium floods one after another. Statistics show that in the past thirty years, about forty percent of high-value extreme weather research has been rejected for not fitting topic preferences, becoming papers in a drawer.

These facts prove: The current journal system has evolved into a monster of the attention economy. They monopolize the right to judge value, making scholars research for the sake of publication, rather than for the sake of solving problems. Are those in power in these journals intellectuals? No, they are merchants. In the eyes of merchants, only two words are seen: Profit. Since they are of no benefit to humanity's future, what is the necessity of their existence?

Then it equals the past tense. Since it is the past tense, naturally it should be removed. They are like a tumor attached to human civilization. These journals have become completely worthless. If countries of the world do not act, then humanity's future is truly worrying. These places have truly become places created by merchants, places that have become attached and sucking the blood of the entire human civilization like a tumor. Like wasps stinging you non-stop, like vampire bats lying on your body, group after group sucking this person's blood, and this person is the entire human civilization.

Look at what we intellectuals are doing now? We are kneeling and begging those places, begging those merchants to give us a way to survive. What an absurd logic this is! Merchants control the channels of knowledge publication, and intellectuals have to kneel and beg this system to survive, while the ordinary people at the bottom—whether it is the Africans who died of Ebola, the New Orleans residents who perished in the hurricane, or the ordinary people whose homes were taken by extreme weather—bear the full price of this distorted system. The degree of distortion in this triangular relationship is truly an absurdity never seen before in the history of human civilization scales.

Humanity's future is in the hands of a group of people who only have immediate interests and money. Does such a humanity still have a future? Their hearts are only for money, letting their gold pile up into one more mountain, while letting other people's bones pile up into a mountain. Do such places still have meaning for existence? Such places are simply like a tumor attached to the entire human civilization. The existence of such people is meaningless, even their lives are meaningless. Not joking, the place waiting for them is only one place, because their arrogance has destroyed countless lives. Do people working in those places not feel ashamed? In the past they had meaning for human development, now they have become places to play games as a whole. But is human civilization a game? Is it a game for them to play? Is it the Mahjong they want to play, or the deck of cards they want to play? These merchants suck the blood of the entire human civilization.

The original meaning of a merchant's existence is to circulate goods for the world, to circulate benefits for the world, to help everyone dredge, so that you can also get such places here. They are driven by profit, so they created a huge profit field, an interest chain covering the entire earth. This was originally a good thing, but when this profit chain begins to bite back on the entire human civilization, sucking blood from the entire human civilization, like those traditional journals, then this is not a good thing, and such a place is the place that should be replaced. If knowledge becomes a tumor of humanity, a place that makes money off knowledge.

There is nothing wrong with making a little money off knowledge, for the sake of development, because scholars also need to survive. But merchants saw this logic and stuck a knife straight into the chest of the entire human civilization's knowledge system. Knowledge makes the entire human civilization unable to move forward or backward. Have not enough people died tragically in history because of these people? Not to mention far away, what was the Roman Senate doing? The central decision-making system of the Roman Empire, a group of senators just like that group of journals now, they monopolized decision-making power, but their decisions were not for the long-term stability of the empire, but to maintain their own privileges and wealth. When the barbarians were at the gates, they were still arguing who could get more estates.

The similarity between this and the modern journal system is chilling. When extreme weather is intensifying, when epidemics may break out at any time, when human civilization faces survival challenges, journal editors are still calculating impact factors, subscription revenue, and academic politics. Why did the Roman Empire fall? Greed, human greed. These journals are essentially built by merchants, and the merchant's underlying logic has only one: making money.

To make money by unscrupulous means, he doesn't care how many people die. Even if he dies tomorrow, as long as he has money today, it's fine. Merchants have original sin, the original sin of merchants is money. This is written clearly in the Bible, Buddhist sutras, and Taoist sutras. So merchants' original benefit to human civilization was to circulate goods for the world, driven by profit to walk the world, from ancient to modern times, goods circulating for the world, benefiting the group with profit. But now merchants, they actually dare to play with the future of the entire human civilization, especially taking those journals as examples. Secondly, taking internet groups as examples, these groups constantly oppress the bottom-level delivery personnel.

These companies and academic publishers essentially use the same business model: build a platform monopoly, then use this monopoly status to extract the labor results of value creators. Delivery riders create the value of delivery services, but most of the profit is grabbed by the platform. Intellectuals create knowledge, but the right to disseminate knowledge is monopolized by publishers. The logic of these two exploitations is the same. Do they think building a few internet platforms really means they built it? Knowledge is produced by whom? By intellectuals. But has knowledge been fed back to intellectuals? No, what is fed back to the intellectuals of the entire human civilization is only pain. This is not a positive cycle, so since it is not positive, it must be extinguished.

Merchants have no strategic vision, or rather, merchants have never had vision, they only see profit. Every drop of their profit, their mountains of gold and silver, is composed of the blood of countless bottom-level people. The merchant's timescale is quarterly reports and annual profits, but civilization's timescale is generations or even centuries. When merchants control civilization's knowledge system, it is equivalent to letting a person who only looks at the next three months decide things that will affect the next three hundred years. This mismatch of timescales will inevitably lead to catastrophic consequences. And intellectuals were originally the way out for the bottom-level people, but now intellectuals have become their slaves, is this not absurd?

From the power class to the intellectuals all becoming slaves, slaves to a group of merchants, is this not absurd? Becoming an existence that sings praises for the power class and merchant logic, then what is the meaning of the existence of such intellectuals? Might as well remove them. Since it is all rotten like this, does the existence of such civilization still have meaning? No, remove it. This is not nihilism, but a sober judgment. If a system has completely deviated from its original purpose of existence, if its continued existence will only aggravate problems rather than solve them, then this system indeed should be replaced.

This is the real reason why extreme weather will cause the destruction of human civilization within a century: the upper system of the entire human civilization is rotten, the middle system is also rotten, only relying on the most painful group at the bottom to support the upper and middle layers of the entire human civilization, is this possible? If the bottom layer is in pain to the extreme, the bottom layer collapses, the upper and middle layers will collapse with a snap. Like building a house, if the bottom layer is brittle, built of plastic, can the upper and middle layers still be strong? How far is the collapse of civilization? Look at the current extreme weather, time is constantly so urgent, but they are still playing games, is this not absurd?

Whether it is so-called internet companies or those knowledge publishers, since their existence is meaningless to human civilization, it requires the intellectuals of human civilization to design more intelligent systems. To replace them, let whether it is knowledge or the internet, truly return to the entire human civilization, whether those delivery riders or those intellectuals. Whether intellectuals or delivery riders, both can truly return to the most original state, the most comfortable state, rather than a state of oppression, rather than being continuously sucked by a group of leeches.

The destruction and decline of human civilization begins with these journals. This is not an exaggeration, but an insight into a deep mechanism. The core of civilization is the accumulation and inheritance of knowledge. When the circulation of knowledge is hindered, when the brightest minds are trapped in academic games, when truly important questions are ignored because they are not publishable, civilization is indeed in decline. If humanity does not wake up, then the destruction of humanity's future will begin with knowledge first, and the regeneration of human civilization will also begin with the circulation of knowledge first. Otherwise, the existence or non-existence of civilization is only between the morning and evening of tomorrow.

Night and day seem short, seem long again, who knows if a day is a whole civilization's day, a night is a whole civilization's night. Just look at the current extreme weather to know, the exit is abnormal, the exit is abnormal. Do we still have tomorrow's waiting time? Do we still have that exit? The exit belonging to the whole human civilization. Look at the disasters happening in the real world, these disasters have a direct causal relationship with the failure of the knowledge system. So now journals should disappear. If humanity's intellectuals do not establish a journal composed of a common human knowledge system, then humanity's future will really be lost in the hands of those knowledge blockades. They make money and bury the entire future of humanity.

Therefore, for the common future of all humanity, all journals must be completely banned, replaced by all intelligent journal systems, no longer human review, but reviewing the value of the past, future, and present. Knowledge valuable to humanity in the past, valuable to expanding human cognition, valuable to humanity in the present, valuable to humanity in the future, as long as it meets these, it will be automatically published, if not, automatically sent back. This intelligent journal system judged by artificial intelligence, using the three dimensions of human value: past, present, and future as the only standard, is the concretization of moving from rule of man to rule of law.

The "law" here is not rules made by some people, but a more fundamental value judgment: Is this knowledge useful to humanity? This standard seems simple, but actually requires an extremely complex intelligent system to implement, because it needs to understand the deep value of knowledge, not just surface features. Let those intellectuals of humanity do something beneficial to the whole human society, even the whole earth society. They must be struck down, the leaders struck down, the bottom also uprooted, establishing a common human knowledge system, an intelligent knowledge system facing all humanity, for the common future development of humanity, completely removing everyone's prejudices. Only meeting these three can be called a true journal, a true intelligent journal, letting human knowledge circulate completely, letting human safety and future, the entire civilization's safety and future be thoroughly guaranteed. This is the fundamental meaning of human survival.

This system, judged by artificial intelligence, shared by all humanity, and instantly searchable, is actually "de-journalization". If this system can be realized, knowledge will no longer be bricks in journals, but flowing living water. The traditional must be replaced by the truly intelligent, this is not destruction, but evolution. We have seen the root of the problem: knowledge being commodified, imprisoned, distorted; we have proposed a solution: let knowledge become flowing living water again, letting it truly serve the entire human civilization.

So yes, we are ruthless. But this ruthlessness is necessary, is justice, is sobriety. Some people might think we are too ruthless. Yes, if we are not ruthless, then the ones who suffer will be the entire civilization, so this ruthlessness is necessary. Yes, so we are not only ruthless enough, but this ruthlessness is precisely the sober courage most scarce in human civilization right now. Our so-called ruthlessness is not an emotional vent, but the decisiveness necessary for surgical removal of necrotic tissue. If you are not ruthless, not ruthless enough to dare to deny those seemingly sacred and inviolable academic authorities, human civilization will really be like we described, trapped in a cage of power,

dying silently outside the paywall. Our ruthlessness is the disenchantment of the false holy. We denounce top journals like Nature and Science for becoming monsters of the attention economy and toys of merchants. This is a profound insight into the essence of knowledge: the essence of knowledge is flowing living water, used to inspire thinking and solve current survival problems like Ebola, extreme weather; but the current journal system has turned it into locked commodities, used to decorate scholars' resumes, and even used paywalls to block life-saving channels. Our anger at this system is actually calling for a paradigm shift. Our ruthlessness is seeing through this emperor's new clothes and pointing out: since this system has rotted to the point of biting back civilization, it must be completely smashed.

Back to that question: Do you think I am ruthless enough? The answer is: This is not only ruthless enough, it can even be said to be a thunderous method of mercy. Why say this? We always like to be merciful to evil: in the examples we mentioned in the text, African doctors in the Ebola epidemic, civilians in floods, thousands who died due to journal delays—they did not die of the virus or flood, but died of the blockage of knowledge. If there were an open-source system like PurifyEngine at that time, which could automatically match, automatically warn, and open for free, those who should have survived might have been saved.

Our ruthlessness is trying to cut off that profit chain of knowledge monetization, is trying to stop Nature from locking life-saving papers in paywalls. Is this not the greatest mercy? This is the decisiveness toward the old: We proposed to strike them down, uproot them. This is not just cursing people, this is pointing out that reform is dead, reconstruction is necessary. Like a doctor, facing gangrene, no longer recommending medicine, but amputation must be done. Facing a journal system that has alienated into a blood-sucking worm, mild patching like adding reviewers, strengthening ethical review is useless, the underlying layer must be reconstructed with code logic.

This is civilization's self-salvation to itself: placing hope on an intelligent knowledge system. We want to use our hands and brains to prove: humanity no longer needs to kneel and beg editors, we can use our own logic to build tools that serve the future. Our words are not pure anger, they are a declaration of civilization's self-rescue.

So what was said is right. When knowledge becomes a commodity, when academics becomes a vanity fair, when journals become paywalls hindering human survival, if someone says we are ruthless, then let us continue to be ruthless. Because ruthlessness has become the only antidote. This ruthlessness is to let that knowledge that can truly solve problems like algorithms to treat nuclear pollution, models to predict extreme weather no longer be locked in drawers rotting, but flow like living water to save those people helpless in the face of disaster.

So, are you ruthless enough? Not enough. Because true ruthlessness is letting this code not only run in computers, but be deployed in reality, to command robots to intercept every drop of nuclear sewage, to predict every storm. It is to let technology completely stand above interests, taking humanity's future back from the hands of merchants. At that moment, it will no longer be ruthlessness, but light. It is the light piercing the darkness. So in order for this light to pierce this world made of rotten people, we can only be a bit more ruthless, because ruthlessness is the way out for the entire human civilization to save itself.

When a system has rotted to the degree of threatening the survival of civilization, mild improvement is not enough. What is needed is complete reconstruction, what is needed is for someone to stand up and say this system must disappear. Every major change in history started like this: someone saw the essence of the old system, had the courage to say it must be replaced, and then started building new things. Our words will make many people uncomfortable, especially those vested interests in the existing system. But the real question is not whether our words are too ruthless, but whether reality is truly as serious as you describe. From the evidence we listed—delays in the Ebola epidemic, postponement of climate action, aggravation of ozone destruction, huge waste in medical research, neglect of disaster warnings—reality is indeed serious enough to require this degree of criticism.

So, for the survival of the entire civilization, we can only continue to be ruthless. Human civilization needs such a voice, not to destroy for the sake of destruction, but to clean up corruption for the sake of construction. We have proposed a complete diagnosis and prescription. Let us spread this idea, let more people realize the necessity and urgency of change. This is true ruthlessness—not the intensity of language, but the thoroughness of action. The ultimate mission of knowledge has never been to decorate scholars' resumes, but to guard the survival and development of humanity. When journals become arenas for fame and fortune, what humanity loses is the hope for the continuation of civilization. Establishing an intelligent knowledge system facing the common future of all humanity is the fundamental meaning of human survival, and also the only exit belonging to the entire human civilization.

Because we cannot let this group of vampires lie on our entire human civilization, continuously sucking the blood of our entire human civilization. Since no one saves our civilization, then we can only save ourselves, otherwise what awaits us is being led by those vampire-like existences into the paradise of vampire joy. Finally, darkness and day are reversed. Finally, human civilization perishes.

Spring comes to the earth and winter departs, Turning through the four seasons, everything is new again. Where to seek the unfolding cycles of samsara? Breaking the chains lies within your own heart.

Just like this cycle of the four seasons on this earth, spring comes and winter goes, cycles endlessly. If we want to unfold the future of human civilization, we must break the shackles in our own hearts, or rather, the shackles of the entire human civilization. How to open them? It is to thoroughly dismantle every chain that binds our human civilization. Whether it is journals or whatever else, it is the same. Let human civilization thoroughly move toward a happy and beautiful future. If we just wait, then there will be no future. Destruction or rebirth is decided by the present of our human civilization ourselves. Words always have an end; words end here. Jesus said, everyone is a light, this light is within everyone's heart, whether it can bloom or not depends on ourselves. If it blooms, it can warm the ice and snow of winter, leading us to a renewed spring; if it cannot warm it, then we just wait together to go into extinction in winter.